

IN ADDITION , IT IS NECESSARY TO ENSURE THAT THE STUDENTS OF THE 9TH AND 10TH GRADES HAVE THE OPPORTUNITY TO PARTICIPATE IN THE ACTIVITIES OF THE SCHOOL

MUHAMMED MARSBEK ULI REYPNAZAROV

Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyoz, independent researcher.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14258312>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 9-noyabr 2024 yil
Ma'qullandi: 19-noyabr 2024 yil
Nashr qilindi: 30-noyabr 2024 yil

KEY WORDS

modes of action, stages of development, problem solution, attributes of balance, speed and strength

ABSTRACT

This article is written about attracting young people to sports and its dynamic balance at home.

The concept of dynamic equilibrium is carefully considered, first of all the concept of action and then the principle of equilibrium. When the action is in dynamic equilibrium, the system returns to a specific norm, and under the influence of external forces, all solutions find their equilibrium. Dynamic balance - when the system is activated. When all forces are equal to zero. If the system is in dynamic equilibrium, it will maintain its equilibrium position.

Several processes are necessary to maintain dynamic equilibrium: - External forces: External forces, such as gravity, must be in proper equilibrium. Speed: The speed of movement ensures the dynamic balance of the system itself. Total friction: The friction between two objects ensures the alignment of the movement.

External forces play a significant role in the process of basketball players' movement. In many cases, external forces are necessary to achieve the goal of the movement. Let's see what happens when we get there. Location of external forces. -gravity: when a basketball player moves on the court, gravity will settle in his place and he will jump. The gravitational force is taken into account and a special place is chosen for the jump. -Friction: When a player's feet come into contact with the court, frictional force is lost. Friction helps to control movement and agility, which means that you need to move around and move fast. -External forces: other players' actions, such as taking the ball or sending a basketball player's actions after a missed pass. These external forces often work in conjunction with friction, gravity, and dynamic forces. Action process. - starting position: the basketball player is ready to move when he is in the starting position.

During this time, he checks his physical condition, his balance. -strength training: The basketball player, for example, should use physical strength to reach the goal without taking the ball, exceed the speed of the goal, lift the legs and use physical strength. In this process, the muscles respond to external forces. -effective movement: When a basketball player is moving on the court, he must take into account the influences that control the friction. In these actions, the current attenuator tries to maintain dynamic equilibrium.

Education is one of the most complex forms of human cognitive activity, significantly accelerating individual psychic development and knowledge acquisition. A teacher doesn't

just impart knowledge in the learning process, but in this process, the learner, the student, is influenced, which makes them more active in their learning, so that the learner becomes an active participant in the learning process.

Theoretical knowledge that is instilled in the minds of students in the process of education is further strengthened through practical activities. A person learns the meaning of events, objects, and events around him by encountering them in the real world. It is only through practical activity that man learns the mysteries of the relations that constitute the process of social, productive activity, as well as the phenomena of nature.

As a result of interacting with objects, objects interact with the senses, and the senses generate perception. In practice, the active thought activity of a person occurs. Using reasoning, he deeply understands reality. When we talk about the importance of practice as a source of knowledge, we also need to emphasize the essence of the cognitive process. Knowledge is a complex dialectical process, a pathway from lively discussion to abstract thought and then to practice. Knowledge is the process of consciously perceiving the essence of things, events, and phenomena that are abstract and unknown to the individual. Knowing objective existence begins with perceiving it.

Perception is the real connection of the mind with the external world. Perception is the mental representation of certain qualities, signs, or events of the world around us that affect our sense organs (we know there are five). So every organ, every analyzer, I'm going to say.

As Pavlov pointed out, it feels some of the most important qualities of things. Perception leads to the conscious perception of the meaning of things and events. Perception is the process by which things and events that affect the mind through the senses are reflected in the mind as a whole.

Imagination occurs in the process of cognition through sensation and perception. Imagination is the trace of perception and perception that remains in the human mind for a long time. Or in other words, an imagination is a vivid emotional representation in the mind of things and events that once affected and perceived the sensory organs. The basketball player is out of position, gravity and friction force him back into position. Its balance and position must always be balanced by external forces. Examples: -sekiriŷ: When a basketball player jumps the ball in the air, the gravity and the dynamics of their movements must be considered. After rotation, its orbit is controlled by friction and gravity. Picking up the ball: When a basketball player picks up the ball, he uses physical force, friction, and accuracy. In this case, forces (other players) also play an important role.

Basketball players have divided the processes that determine the accuracy of the action into three groups: objective; subjective; the physical characteristics of the ball, which affect the player's body; the mechanical characteristics of the ball, which affect the player's body - all of which are considered to be objective or external. Adaptation to subjective processes involves processes that are related to the working conditions of the athlete. They may be distinguished by purely individual characteristics: physical appearance, sex, age, etc. Other people are not dependent on individual characteristics and basketball is for every person who loves it (M. Stradina). C to C., 2005).

Description of the psychological and functional state of the athlete, training methods, methods of performing movements in the indoor environment, etc. These factors determine in the first place the behavior of the athlete and his work activity. Each student can play basketball regardless of other individual abilities (M. Stradina). C to C., 2005). This is a description of the psychological and functional state of the athlete; a training method; a method of performing actions in the event of the game and others. The first of these processes indicates that the athlete's hand is thin and that he is washed clean.

It is advisable to use a large number of repetitions of movements from a specifically defined position until the skill of the basketball players is established to a certain degree. At the age of 16-17 years old, the ability to self-regulate has been strengthened, and the ability to use a

more complex decision-making system than the previous one. Hand-operated saws of this type are operated from a distance exceeding the face-to-face distance of the saws, and then from the distance of the glass. This is preferable to the step-step method, which limits the distance from the man to the man. Improvement of precision in recent years.

In sports schools, the participation rate was 31.7% in the preliminary teams, 65% in the secondary teams, and 3.3% in the sports teams. 9-10 young people in the basic training group, 12-16 young people in the fluid training group, 16-20 young people in the sports training group. In order to develop the basic principles of the school curriculum, children are trained to become a universal school teacher. He continued these principles in the, but later added elements of the speak. In the sports teams, the basic principles are expressed in the preparations, the basis of which is also taken into account and the team. technical preparation team's mission is to stop the technical-casual movements, turnaround tours, kick-off tours, jet-carriers, and be the manager of the jury.

References:

1. Basketball by Yu Portnov. C and. M to. February 1988
2. Basketball team. Muhin N. M to. February 1989.
3. Basketball Semashko from N. C and. M to. French 1976
4. Methodical tools for basketball. Donchenko by V. T is. Medical 1986.
5. Sports games Kovalev V. M to. Fis, 1988,
6. Sports Games by Godin M. The A. M Fis 1991
7. Tactics of the game of basketball. The A. by Tomelsky. M to. FIS for the year 1966.
8. M. Zhukov. N and N. - M.: Moving games: Training. for study. ped. high school. Publishing center "Academy" 2000. - 160 c.

INNOVATIVE
ACADEMY